

A NEW TECHNIQUE FOR THE MEASUREMENT OF GLASS FIBER ORIENTATION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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The technique is based on the diffraction effect of glass fibers and their radiographic images using a light beam. The sample is a 100-200 μm thick section of composite material if the polymeric matrix is light transparent; otherwise, the Contact-Microradiography is examined. A small He-Ne laser tube is employed as light source on an optical bench. In a few seconds the angular distribution curve of fibers in the volume investigated is detected. Fiber or whisker flow models can be examined in a steady and non-steady state. Another feature of the technique is to allow the complete automation of the data acquisition step, thus obtaining a plotted map of fiber orientation for a very large sample in a very short time.

INTRODUCTION

The flow orientation of short fibers in composite materials is known as an important problem in composite industry. The main trouble is to resolve theoretically, in a suitable form, the fiber motion in the flow $\sqrt{1}$, $\sqrt{2}$. The experimental measurement of fiber orientation is thus the tool to an empirical approach to the problem. Some authors employed this approach $\sqrt{2}$, 3, $\sqrt{4}$ but their methods require long measuring times and large practical troubles in extensive and quantitative measurements of fiber orientation. The most used techniques in orientation measurement of glass fibers are:

- manual counting directly in the sample or by Contact-Microradiography $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{5}$;
- inspection of composite internal surfaces previously cutted out, polished and chemical-etched $\sqrt{6}$.

Some reduction in counting time was obtained by drawing fibers (metallic or coloured) $\sqrt{7}$.

At the present time, the computer analysis of stereoscan-microscope images of composites is a speedy and reliable technique in orientation studies but has its greatest disadvantage in a very expensive apparatus. An inexpensive, rapid and reliable technique is thus of interest.

EXPERIMENTALS

Measurements of short fiber orientation are carried out either directly on the specimen or by means of Contact-Microradiography. In this context the optical diffraction effect given by glass fibers and their radiographic images are used. The optical beam employed to enlighten the specimen is a monochromatic random polarised red beam (laser beam). A white parallel beam could also be employed.

The experimental apparatus is sketched in Fig. 1. The laser beam irradiates a circular area of the specimen (thin sample section or related radiographic plate). Here, the beam intensity is splitted into two parts. The transmitted beam continues its pathway towards the screen placed behind the sample. The second part of the beam is deviated from the right direction and draws a diffraction pattern on the screen. The screen is containing two rotating rectangular slits placed symmetrically with respect to the transmitted beam direction. The lens after the screen sends the pattern intensity passing through the slits into the light detector. By turning at constant angular speed the screen and then the slits, the angular intensity distribution of the diffraction pattern is measured. The measurement is made on the circular crown drawn by the slits. The range of the α angle is $0 \leq \alpha \leq \pi$.

The diffraction pattern of many objects is biunivocally connected to the physical and geometrical features of diffracting objects and their spatial arrangement. In thin sections of composite glass-reinforced material the diffracting objects are ideal glass cylinders differently oriented through the volume investigated. The radiographic picture of a glass fiber is a rectangular transparent slit on a dark background. The theory on diffraction effects of glass fibers is formally the same as that for radiographic section pictures and is reported below.

As an example, a typical result obtained for an injection moulded composite is reported. The composite is Nylon 6 reinforced by 30% weight of glass fibers of 15 μm diameter. A thin section (120 μm thick) was cutted out from the sample by means of a slow speedy diamond saw Micro-slice type. The Contact-Microradiography of the section was obtained by $\text{FeK}\alpha$ irradiation on Ilford L4 Nuclear plate and enlightened by a laser tube in a 1.0 mm diameter area.

Fig. 2 shows the correlation between a radiographic picture (magn. 40 X) (a), the corresponding diffraction pattern (b) and the measured angular distribution of the diffraction pattern intensity (I_c) and manual counting of fiber orientation (I_{Ic}) according to (a).

Measurements made on composite sections perpendicular to the main orientation axis are not trustworthy because the fibers projection on the radiographic plate is circular in form and the diffraction pattern is the same as in the random orientation. A preliminary visual inspection of the plate is therefore necessary. Fiber fragments having small aspect ratio give a constant intensity contribution over the en-

tire range of the α angle. The highest accuracy is obtained by background determination. To this purpose, a small reference sample (polymer film without fibers) is exposed together with the reinforced section. Results of the same accuracy are obtained when the measurements are carried out directly on the sample section. The composite section is set between two parallel glass plates containing a liquid wetting the polymeric material and having an equal refraction index. This improvement eliminates the large surface scattering effect produced by surface roughness.

Finally, an angular resolution of 2° can easily be achieved by a suitable slit design, as seen in the appendix.

DATA ANALYSIS

The light intensity angular distribution $f(\alpha)$, detected and corrected for background as shown previously, is proportional to the angular distribution density of fiber projections lying at $\beta = \alpha \mp \pi/2$ in the screen; α is referred to the z-axis. Experimental studies indicate that a more significant data analysis is obtained by statistical methods. This approach involves the systematic orientation measurement of fiber angular distribution following a suitable map (e.g. a square grid). The angular fiber distribution is evaluated statistically by the following parameters: mean orientation angle β_m ; peak orientation angle β_p ; angular orientation spread σ ; orientation index I. A useful, condensed way to present the orientation characteristics for a composite section is shown in Fig. 3. The statistical parameters β_m , β_p , σ and I of angular fiber distribution in a point of the map are defined in the left, lower hand of the page and are presented graphically as shown on the right hand side by an oriented parallelogram. The upper map is thus obtained by automatically plotting the β_m , β_p , σ , I and x, y coordinates for the set of measured points in the reinforced thin section.

The sample in Fig. 3 is the half mean section of a injection moulded ball-drop ASTM sample where the polymeric material is Nylon 6.

As a future development, the complete automation of the measurements can be reached by a computer system which also performs the data acquisition step on the sample and calculates, in every point, the statistical parameters mentioned above.

THEORY OF FIBER ORIENTATION MEASUREMENT BY OPTICAL DIFFRACTION

The diffraction effect involved in fiber orientation measurements is known as "Fraunhofer" diffraction and consists of scattering of the light beam intensity by the body in directions away from the beam direction. The light intensity $I(\underline{r})$ diffracted in direction \underline{r} by the fiber follows the general Eq. $\int \frac{8}{7}$.

$$I(\underline{r}) = D^2(\underline{r}) \cdot I_0 \quad (1)$$

where I is the impinging intensity beam and D is the diffraction scalar function. The D function involves geometrical and optical features of the diffracting body and, also, the light wavelength of the beam. The coarse diffraction pattern symmetry is strictly connected with the coarse symmetry of the diffracting body. Thus, generally spoken, the measurement of the symmetry element orientation in the diffraction pattern, is a suitable way to detect the orientation of the body itself. The glass fiber is a "slender cylinder". Let us assume that the fiber length L is infinite in respect to the diameter d, being the aspect ratio L/d usually high. A slender cylinder has, in almost any position, a shadow area which is virtually a rectangle; its sides b and c are the shadows of d and L respectively. When the fiber is perpendicular to the beam, its diffraction pattern is non zero only in the plane ω which is perpendicular to the fiber itself and we find $\int \frac{9}{7}$

$$D^2(\underline{r}) = D^2(\theta) = \frac{\sin^2(\pi \cdot b \cdot \sin \theta / \lambda)}{(\pi \cdot b \cdot \sin \theta / \lambda)^2} \quad (2)$$

where θ is the observation angle of the diffracted intensity beam measured from the lighting beam direction and λ is the light wavelength. It is easy to show that $D^2(\theta)$ function is positive and has its principal maximum symmetrically centered at $\theta = 0$, between $-\lambda/b \leq \sin \theta \leq \lambda/b$; the secondary peaks are between $n \cdot \lambda/b \leq \sin \theta \leq (n+1) \cdot \lambda/b$ and are very small compared to the principal one (area ratio < 0.035) and are vanish-

ing as θ increases. Thus, the principal maximum of the diffraction pattern is the most suitable for fiber orientation measurements. For a glass fiber dipped in air and irradiated by a red laser beam we find experimentally that $b/d \approx 0.8$. The ratio b/d is changing with the refraction index of the fiber in the surrounding matter. With the fiber not perpendicular to the beam the diffraction function D is non zero in a curved surface of paraboloid, symmetrical shape. It can be shown but it is also an experimental result that this fact does not have negative implications because the orientation measurement involves small values of θ , around the beam direction. Practically, we can assume that the diffraction pattern range used in the measurements ($-3^\circ < \theta < 3^\circ$) is always in the ω plane, perpendicular to the fiber shadow, and the solution is always the Eq. (2) even if the fiber is not perpendicular to the laser beam.

When we make the microradiographic picture of the fiber, we obtain a narrow transparent slit in a dark background on the photographic plate. The slit sides b' and c' are the shadows of d and L , respectively, in the X-ray lighting. The diffraction pattern for a slit of infinite length is also given in the optical theory and is always the Eq. (2) where only b is changed by b' . The theory is in very good agreement with experimental results even when the sides of the fiber microradiographic picture are broad lines. The very important point outlines is that in the small θ range used both fiber and radiographic picture give the same diffraction pattern from a qualitative point of view with equal orientation. Thus, the diffraction pattern for a cloud of fibers and for the radiographic picture of the cloud can be dealt with in the same way as the orientation measurements. Let us look at the experimental features and conditions.

As in Fig. 1, the screen is mounted perpendicularly to the light beam behind the sample and collects the diffraction pattern. The origin of the cartesian system is in the sample-beam cross-point and the X axis is parallel to the beam direction. The orientation angle of the fiber shadow on the screen α is referred to the X axis. We know that α and β are related by: $\beta = \alpha \mp \pi/2$ and β is the particular fiber diffraction pattern orientation angle. $N_\alpha = dN/d\alpha$ is the amount of fiber shadows oriented at α degrees and, finally, $I_\beta(\theta)$ is the total light intensity diffracted at θ degrees by the N_α fibers or X-ray fiber pictures.

Following the results obtained by Sommerfeld for a cloud of spherical particles [8], it can be shown that, in the range of small θ values of our diffraction pattern, we find:

$$\bar{I}_\beta(\theta) = I_0 \cdot D^2(\theta) \cdot N_\alpha \quad (3)$$

The light intensity $\bar{I}_\beta(\theta)$ is the statistical mean value of $I_\beta(\theta)$ over the surroundings of θ . Also the fiber diameter d must be substituted by its mean value \bar{d} when we deal with a cloud of real glass fibers.

By integrating (3) over the maximum θ range of the main peak we find:

$$W(\beta) = \int_{-\sin^{-1}(\lambda/b)}^{\sin^{-1}(\lambda/b)} I_0 \cdot D^2(\theta) \cdot N_\alpha \cdot d\theta = I_0 \cdot N_\alpha \cdot \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} x^{-2} \cdot \sin^2 x \cdot dx \quad (4)$$

In (4) it is shown that the total intensity $W(\beta)$ at β degrees in the diffraction pattern is proportional to the N_α amount of fibers being

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} x^{-2} \cdot \sin^2 x \cdot dx = \text{const.} \approx 1.41 \quad (5)$$

Thus, the detection of $W(\beta)$ is a suitable orientation measurement for a cloud of fibers.

RESOLUTION LIMIT

We use the approximation $\sin(\lambda/b) \approx \lambda/b$.

If we detect $W(\beta)$ over the range $-\lambda/b \leq \theta \leq \lambda/b$ by a rectangular slit as large as the beam diameter Φ we have a high signal intensity also because of the presence of the transmitted beam but a low angular resolution and a high noise level. A good resolution ϵ is reached by neglecting $I_\beta(\theta)$ in the lower θ range.

By darkening the slit in the range $-0.3 \cdot (\lambda/\bar{b}) \leq \theta \leq 0.3 \cdot (\lambda/\bar{b})$ we detect only $0.3 \cdot W(\beta)$ (the calculation is made on the $D^2(\theta)$ function). The angular half-peak spreading $\epsilon_{.5}$ of the fibers diffracting into the slit opening with more than half of their detectable intensity is

$$\epsilon_{.5} = 2 \cdot \Phi \cdot b / \lambda \quad (6)$$

where R is the fibers-slit distance.

Other similar slit shapes are possible but they are more tedious to build and their gain in angular resolution is not very interesting.

REFERENCES

- 1 CALOW, C.A. and WAKELIN, R.J., J. of the Institute of Metals, Vol. 96, 1968, pp. 2459-2465.
- 2 BELL, J.P., J. Composite Materials, Vol. 3, 1969, pp. 244-253.
- 3 GOETHLER, L.A., Proc. of 25th Annual Tec. Conf., The Soc. of Plastic Industry, Section 14-A, 1970.
- 4 SCHMIDT, L.R., Adv. in Chem. Series, No 142, 1975, Norbert A.J. Platzner Ed., pp. 415-430.
- 5 DARLINGTON, M.W., Mc.GINLEY, P.L., SMITH, G.R., I. Mat. Science, Vol. 11, 1976, pp. 877-886.
- 6 DARLINGTON, M.W. and Mc.GINLEY, P.L. J., Mat. Science, Vol. 10, 1975, pp.906-910.
- 7 KACIR, L., NARKIS, M., ISHAI, O., Pol. Eng. and Science, Vol. 17, 1977, pp. 824-834.
- 8 SOMMERFIELD, A., Optics, Academic Press Inc., New York, Third Printing, 1964.
- 9 VAN DE HUST, H.C., Light Scattering by small Particles, John Wiley & Sons Inc., 1964.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3